

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

A breeding method for tolerance for acid sulfate soil

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Tolerance for acid sulfate soils is related to tolerance for Al toxicity, Fe toxicity, and P deficiency. Local varieties have all three characteristics, modern varieties or lines only one or two.

We crossed high-yielding varieties with local tolerant varieties and modern varieties with different tolerances. Crossing modern varieties with different tolerances gave quicker and more effective results because negative traits of local varieties did not need to be eliminated.

Among six crosses, the cross NN75-2/V12 gave the best performance. NN75-2 is an intermediate variety with tolerance for Al toxicity and P deficiency, V12 is a high-yielding

Tolerance for acid sulfate soils among different varieties and crosses. Hanoi, Vietnam.

	Score ^a			
	Al toxicity tolerance	P deficiency tolerance	Fe toxicity tolerance	Acid sulfate soils tolerance
IR8	7	5	5	5-1
Bau	1	1	1-2	1
V12	3	5	3-5	3-5
NN75-2	1	1	5	2-3
IR2151-9-6	1	1	3-4	1-2
IR2153-2-6	1	1	5	2-3
IR8/Bau	1	1	3	1-3
V12/NN75-2	1	1	3	1-3
NN75-2/V12 (V14)	1	1	3	1
IR8/NN75-2	5	1	5-7	3-5
V12/IR2151-9-6	1	1	3-5	1-3
V12/IR2153-2-6	1-3	1-3	5	5

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

semidwarf variety with relatively high tolerance for Fe toxicity.

From this cross, we selected line V14, with good plant type, large panicles, moderate resistance to blast, and high cold tolerance. With these traits, V14 could be grown in the spring on acid

sulfate soils in the north.

In varietal testing in different soil types, V14 gave 10–15% higher yield than NN75-2, a variety adapted to acid and acid sulfate soils, and yield similar to that of IR8 on nonacid soil (see table). □

Performance of coarse and fine rice varieties on alkali soils

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In 1986 we evaluated selected varieties in 40 farmers' fields in 7 villages of the Operational Research Project for reclamation of alkali soils. Soils were highly alkali (pH > 10.0), sandy loam in

texture, and are classified as Natrustalfs (see table).

The fields were bunded and leveled and gypsum (30 mesh) applied Jun–Jul 1986. For IR8, PR106, PR107, and Basmata varieties, 120 kg N/ha and 6 kg Zn/ha were applied. For B370 and Basmati Desi, N was reduced to 80 kg/ha.

Maximum yield was with IR8 (4.6 t/ha) followed by PR106, PR107,

Basmata, B370, and Basmati Desi. Basmata, with an average yield of 4.0 t/ha, had the maximum return — \$881/ha — because of its higher sale price (see figure). □

B-370 (Basmati) and Basmata varieties of rice have similar grains but differ in yield potential. Karnal, India, 1986.

Grain yield of different rice varieties in first year of reclamation of alkali soils. Karnal, India, 1986.

Variety	Fields (no.)	Av pH 1:2	Gypsum applied	Grain yield (t/ha)	Sale price ^a (\$/t)	Gross return ^a (\$/ha)
IR8	1	10.2	10.5	4.6	128	589
PR106	6	10.2	10.5	4.5	135	605
PR107	3	10.1	10.0	4.4	135	592
Basmata	16	10.1	10.5	4.0	220	881
Basmati (B370)	10	10.0	10.0	1.6	384	631
Basmati Desi	4	10.2	10.5	1.5	340	506

^aConverted at the rate of \$1 = Rs 12.49.

Vyttila 3, a new rice variety for acid saline areas

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Vyttila 3 has been released for acid saline areas of Kerala. The Vyttila 1/Taichung Native 1 cross yields 200 kg/ha more than improved pureline selection Vyttila 1.

Vyttila 3, with 115 d duration, is

Performance of Vyttila 3 in farmers' fields, Kerala, India.

Location	Yield (t/ha)	
	Vyttila 1	Vyttila 3
Parur	0.9	1.3
Vyttila	3.6	3.8
Maradu	2.4	2.4
Panangad	3.7	4.0
Chellanam	4.5	5.0
Kandekadavu	4.3	4.1
Kannamali	4.5	4.9
Mean	3.4	3.6

suitable for May-Jun to Sep-Oct (pokkali season) cultivation. It is 166 cm tall with 3.6 t/ha average yield potential and 5 t/ha maximum yield potential (see table). Kernels are red with good cooking quality; protein content is 7.8%.

The variety is photoperiod insensitive and tolerant of major diseases and most insect pests (except stem borer, leafroller, and rice bug). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Chhomro — a promising cold-tolerant traditional rice variety for rainfed wetlands in western hills in Nepal

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No improved rice varieties have yet been identified for temperate regions, particularly for elevations above 1,500 m. We evaluated 57 local varieties and 367 exotic materials during 1985-86. Local rices were collected from the altitude range 1,000-2,300 m in the western hills. Major sources of exotic materials were the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN), the National Cold Tolerance Rice Nursery (NCTRN), and an initial evaluation trial (IET) carried out in collaboration with the National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur.

Cold tolerance screening nurseries were established at LAC (1,500 m). Mean air temperatures during early seedling growth (Jun-Jul) were 16.2-17.1 °C minimum and 22.6-22.8 °C maximum. During ripening (Oct-Nov), minimum temperature was 9.9-15.2 °C and maximum was 16.7-20.1 °C. Maximum water temperature was 20.1 °C in Jul and 14.0 °C in Oct. Cold tolerance of local and exotic varieties was measured by leaf discoloration at seedling stage, spikelet sterility, and grain yield.

Table 1. Comparative performance of selected cold-tolerant rice varieties identified in different nurseries. LAC, 1985-86.

Trial or nursery	Best yielding varieties	Grain yield (t/ha) at 12% moisture content	Sterility ^d (%)	Cold injury at seedling stage ^e (1-9 scale)
Farmers' field, 1985 (n= 13)	Chhomro local	5.3	0	1
	Banahu local	5	.05	3
	Ghara local	3.4	15	3
NCTRN, 1985 (n = 30)	Laisika-F	4.2	20	3
	WR10072-79-1-2-3	2.4	25	3
	NR10068-60-3-2	2.2	25	4
IRCTN, 1985 (n = 184)	Laisika-I	5.1	5	3
	K39-96-1-1-1-2	4.9	5	4
NCTRN, 1986 (n = 22)	Chhomro local	4.8	0	1
	NR10073-167-3-1-3	4.1	30	4
	Phalame	3.4	60	4
LRCTN ^a , 1986 (n = 52)	Chhomro local	5.0	2	1
	Seto Bhakunde	3.9	2	2
	Kalo Patle	3.2	1	2
	Raksali	3.1	5	3
PON ^b , 1986 (n = 50)	Banahu local	4.1	6	2
	Chhomro local	4.0	5	1
	Raksali	2.8	10	3
SFT ^c , 1986 (n = 36)	Chhomro local	4.1	0	1

^a Local Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. ^b Preliminary Observation Nursery. ^c Spacing × Fertility Trial on Chhomro local. ^d Spikelet sterility was estimated by eye and by grasping the panicle. ^e Measured according to the procedures mentioned in the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale.

Table 2. Comparative performance of 2 best cold-tolerant local varieties of rice at an altitude of 1500 m.^a LAC, 1985-86.

Variety	Plant stand/m ²	Tillers/plant	Panicles/m ²	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
Chhomro local	46.6 ± 3.27	7.0 ± 1.05	256.6 ± 34.71	4.798 ± 0.475
Raksali local	29.4 ± 4.48	5.6 ± 0.70	263.3 ± 52.30	2.359 ± 0.794
Difference (P = 0.05)	17.2 ns	1.4 ns	6.7 ns	2.439***

^a Yields were estimated from 1 m² crop cuts (n = 10) from seed multiplication block. ^b At 12% moisture content.